

High-Entropy Alloys

A Flexible Theory for Catalysis: Learning Alkaline Oxygen Reduction on Complex Solid Solutions within the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru Composition Space**

Christian M. Clausen,* Olga A. Krysiak, Lars Banko, Jack K. Pedersen,
Wolfgang Schuhmann, Alfred Ludwig, and Jan Rossmeisl*

Abstract: Compositionally complex materials such as high-entropy alloys and oxides have the potential to be efficient platforms for catalyst discovery because of the vast chemical space spanned by these novel materials. Identifying the composition of the most active catalyst materials, however, requires unraveling the descriptor-activity relationship, as experimentally screening the multitude of possible element ratios quickly becomes a daunting task. In this work, we show that inferred adsorption energy distributions of *OH and *O on complex solid solution surfaces within the space spanned by the system Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru are coupled to the experimentally observed electrocatalytic performance for the oxygen reduction reaction. In total, the catalytic activity of 1582 alloy compositions is predicted with a cross-validated mean absolute error of 0.042 mA/cm² by applying a theory-derived model with only two adjustable parameters. Trends in the discrepancies between predicted electrochemical performance values of the model and the measured values on thin film surfaces subsequently provide insight into the alloys' surface compositions during reaction conditions. Bridging this gap between computationally modeled and experimentally observed catalytic activities, not only reveals insight into the underlying theory of catalysis but also takes a step closer to realizing exploration and exploitation of high-entropy materials.

Introduction

Recently, research into high-entropy materials has been gathering momentum, and new insights have emerged on the synthesis,^[1–5] stability,^[6–8] properties,^[9,10] and catalytic performance in various reactions.^[11–20] This class of materials is characterized by disordered crystalline phases with several principal elements,^[21,22] the prime example being compositionally complex solid solutions (CCSSs) such as high-entropy alloys (HEAs). Even on a single-faceted surface, this type of material will sport innumerable unique surface atom arrangements or binding site motifs due to stochastically distributed surface atoms of different elements^[23] and will accordingly have a characteristic distribution of adsorption energies for each adsorbate species.^[24,25] We argue that said distribution will be essential in evaluating the surface properties.

In catalysis, the canonical descriptor-based method usually relates the adsorption energy of a reaction intermediate on a specific binding site to the catalytic activity because the adsorption strength correlates with the activation energy of the reaction step, as described by Brønsted-Evans-Polanyi relations,^[26,27] and the activation or desorption of the intermediate, both summarized in the Sabatier principle.^[28] Consequently, if a selection of unique sites is available, it is logical to represent the surface's capability of catalysis as the capability of all sites weighted by each site's prevalence i.e. the adsorption energy distributions. When several binding sites in conjunction are required for the reaction mechanism to occur the modeling will get increasingly complicated, however the notion of evaluating the sum of contributions from each collection of sites remains the same.

[*] C. M. Clausen, Dr. J. K. Pedersen, Prof. J. Rossmeisl
Center for High-Entropy Alloy Catalysis (CHEAC), Department of
Chemistry, University of Copenhagen
Universitetsparken 5, 2100 Copenhagen (Denmark)
E-mail: cmc@chem.ku.dk
jan.rossmeisl@chem.ku.dk

Dr. O. A. Krysiak, Prof. W. Schuhmann
Analytical Chemistry—Center for Electrochemical Sciences (CES),
Faculty of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Ruhr University Bochum
Universitätsstrasse 150, 44780 Bochum (Germany)

Dr. L. Banko, Prof. A. Ludwig
Materials Discovery and Interfaces, Institute for Materials, Ruhr
University Bochum
Universitätsstrasse 150, 44780 Bochum (Germany)

[**] A previous version of this manuscript has been deposited on a
preprint server (<https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-szl7b>).

© 2023 The Authors. Angewandte Chemie International Edition
published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under
the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which
permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided
the original work is properly cited.

The adsorption energy distributions of interest are entirely determined by the reaction. In electrochemical reduction of oxygen (ORR) *OH and *O have long been known to be key reaction intermediates and their adsorption energies should govern the rate of catalysis as shown in many previous studies on ordered surfaces.^[29–33]

In this study, we utilize the CCSS system Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru to investigate how theory and experiments can mutually converge towards a common understanding of the catalytic reaction in a less sequential manner than usual. The scientific questions we address are as follows: Are distributions of adsorption energies a better descriptor of catalytic activity than the composition? Is the theory previously developed the best model for ORR catalysis? Can we use the trends in experimentally observed catalytic activity and the distributions of adsorption energies to fit a model based on data and not on an a priori hypothesis regarding the reaction path? And can we reveal real physical differences between surface and volume composition by comparing systematic differences between theory and experiments?

To answer these questions, we have measured the catalytic ORR activity of 1582 alloys from the composition space of the CCSS system Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru. These measurements were conducted by scanning droplet cell (SDC) experiments on thin film materials libraries synthesized using combinatorial co-sputtering from pure elements in such a way as to ensure a good sampling of the activity trends within the entire composition space. The experimentally measured current density at 850 mV vs. RHE was then used to fit and benchmark combinations of input features and models to find a reliable approach for predicting

catalytic ORR activity in the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru composition space, as visualized in Figure 1. We observe that the best model leverages the combination of the inferred adsorption energy distributions of CCSS surfaces and a theory-derived model to not only produce robust predictions but also extend them to alloys containing elements not included in the samples used to fit the model.

Not all trends are captured by said model; however, we hypothesize that this is due to the aforementioned discrepancy between the as-deposited volume composition and the actual surface composition during ORR conditions. The results show that combining high-throughput experiments with machine-learning-inferred descriptors not only provides a viable method of systematic catalyst discovery in an uncharted high-dimensional CCSS composition space but also valuable insight into descriptor-activity relations.

Results and Discussion

Five materials libraries were created by co-deposition of Ag, Pd, Pt, and Ru and all ternary subsets of those four elements, e.g., Ag–Pd–Pt, Ag–Pd–Ru, etc., to ensure a thorough sampling of both the ternary surfaces and quaternary domain of the composition space visualized in Figure 2a. The sputter deposition procedure is detailed in earlier publications.^[34–36] To verify the composition of the thin films in the libraries, 81 energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) measurements were performed for each materials library. These measurements were used to interpolate across the surface area, estimating the composi-

Figure 1. Schematic overview of a workflow for predicting catalytic ORR activity of a CCSS surface composition. a) Three-dimensional simplex showing the composition space of the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru system. Sampled compositions from a thin film materials library are colored according to current density values measured at 850 mV vs. RHE. b) Column of several possible input features from which activity prediction can occur. From the volume composition of the as-deposited thin film, the adsorption energy distribution of the surface can be obtained by an inference model trained on *OH and *O adsorption. By simulating inter-adsorbate interactions, the adsorbate coverage is estimated and the distribution of adsorption energies modified accordingly. c) Column with a selection of models that, fitted to one of the previous input features, can predict the ORR current density at a selected potential indicated by a star. d) Linear sweep voltammograms (LSVs) of all sampled areas on the materials library similarly colored according to the current density at 850 mV vs. RHE indicated by the dashed vertical line.

Figure 2. Overview of the experimentally sampled alloy compositions. a) The three-dimensional simplex of the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru composition space, where the corners, edges, and surfaces of the simplex represent the pure elements, binary alloys, and ternary alloys, respectively. All sampled alloy compositions are colored according to the color scale indicating the measured current density at 850 mV vs. RHE. b) The two-dimensional simplex showing the sampled compositions on the Pd–Pt–Ru surface of the quaternary domain. c) 330 LSVs measured from the Pd–Pt–Ru materials library included in this study.

tion of the thin film for each electrochemical measurement area (cf. Figure S1). Subsequently, using a SDC setup,^[34,35] the ORR activity was measured at 342 different measurement areas on each library, yielding a linear sweep voltammogram (LSV) corresponding to a specific alloy composition for each measurement. The LSVs were measured from 950 to 0 mV vs. RHE, and the electrolyte was kept at pH 12.5 for all experiments. The alkaline electrolyte is an unlikely choice for Pt-group metals, due to more abundant elements being efficient for alkaline ORR.^[37,38] However, we have earlier observed pronounced corrosion on Ag-containing thin films in acidic media^[34] and therefore we chose alkaline to enhance stability and suppress changes to the as-deposited surface composition. Additional details about EDX spectroscopy, SDC setup and electrochemical measurements can be found in the Supporting Information. After the exclusion of 128 LSVs containing high levels of noise, a total of 1582 measurements were approved for further study, cf. Figures S5–S8.

A discrepancy was observed between some LSVs from the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru and Ag–Pt–Ru libraries, despite the as-deposited alloy composition of the measurement areas differing by less than 2%. Examining these data points, an offset in current density between the two libraries was identified, as seen in Figure S9. The mean discrepancy of the similar compositions was found to be 0.103 mA/cm² at 850 mV vs. RHE, and we applied this as a negative correction to all Ag–Pt–Ru experiments. Applying a positive correction to the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru experiments would have caused a divide between the measurements where the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru samples are in close proximity to the Pd–Pt–Ru samples. By performing the former correction, we obtain a clear gradient in the observed current densities at 850 mV vs. RHE across the whole composition space, as seen in Figure 2a.

We used several types of input features to predict the experimentally measured current densities. The simplest of these features was the as-deposited volume composition in the form of a vector. Additionally, we used adsorption

energy distributions of *OH and *O generated from simulating a randomized surface with the corresponding alloy composition. However, obtaining enough adsorption energies to represent the myriad surface-adsorbate interactions possible on an HEA surface is infeasible without a regression algorithm, as even cost-efficient methods like density functional theory (DFT) would require exceptional amounts of computing resources to calculate enough samples.

To address this, we employed an adsorption energy inference model in the form of an earlier published graph neural network (GNN) with a lean architecture.^[39] This inference model was trained using multiple datasets of DFT calculations of *OH and *O on an fcc(111) surface with broadly sampled compositions within the Ag–Ir–Pd–Pt–Ru composition space, as this was readily available to us from the earlier work.^[39] The composite dataset also included several suballoys, e.g., binary, ternary, and quaternary combinations of Ag–Ir–Pd–Pt–Ru. In total, 25,499 DFT samples were included and split into training, validation, and test sets with a 70:15:15 ratio, with all suballoys being represented equally in each set. See the Supporting Information for details on the DFT calculations included and the training procedure of the GNN.

The GNN inference had an overall test mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.045 eV and 0.052 eV for *OH and *O, respectively, with no significant change in performance for any suballoys, as seen in Figure S10. This allowed us to reproduce the adsorption energy distribution of *OH and *O for any alloy within the majority of the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru composition space. However, when using the GNN to infer the adsorption energies of a surface composed mainly of a single element, the increasing homogeneity of the surface causes the number of unique sites to drop. Fewer unique predictions increase the risk of a non-negligible mean error of predicted adsorption energies, which could significantly impact the modeling of the catalytic activity. Therefore, we limited individual elements to a maximum fraction of 80 atomic percent (at.%).

For each experimental LSV included in the study, the measurement area was simulated as a $96 \times 96 \times 3$ atom-sized fcc(111) surface with the corresponding alloy composition. The adsorption energies of all binding site motifs were evaluated with the trained GNN, which resulted in 9,216 adsorption energies for both *OH occupying ontop sites and *O occupying fcc hollow sites, respectively. This constituted the gross adsorption energy distribution for that particular alloy composition. Subsequently, we simulated the occupation of binding sites according to the lowest adsorption energy and mimic inter-adsorbate blocking, which have also been described in detail elsewhere.^[39] From this simulation and the resulting adsorbate coverage, we obtain the net adsorption energy distribution of *OH and *O. The gross and net adsorption energy distributions of *OH and *O, along with the as-deposited volume composition, constitute a total of five sets of features that can be used as input to the prediction models, as sketched in Figure 1b.

To evaluate the performance of combinations of input features and models, the five materials libraries constituted five folds in a cross-validation scheme where one library was left as a test set and the model was fitted to the remaining four libraries. This was repeated with all five libraries as test sets, and the combined test set errors were used for evaluating the MAE. This “leave-one-out” scheme ensures that the model is capable of extrapolating predictions to unexplored parts of the composition space and not just interpolating locally between experiments.

In previous work,^[34,35,39] we have applied a theory-derived model to the adsorption energies of *OH and *O based on the Butler–Volmer and Koutecký–Levich equations:

$$j_{k,i} = b \cdot e^{-\frac{|\Delta G_i - \Delta G_{opt}| + 0.86 - eU}{k_B T}} \quad (1)$$

$$j = \frac{a}{N_{surf}} \sum_i^{N_{ads}} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{1-b} + \frac{1}{j_{k,i}}} \quad (2)$$

Where $j_{k,i}$ is the kinetically limited current of site i with ΔG_i being the adsorption energy of the binding site and j being the current density of the surface, taking into account the diffusion limit of individual sites but not the transport limitation of reactants to and from the surface. N_{surf} and N_{ads} are the numbers of sites on the surface, here being 9,216 for each type of adsorbate, and the number of sites where adsorption with either *OH or *O has occurred. For the gross adsorption energy distributions $N_{ads} = N_{surf}$ and for the net distributions $N_{ads} < N_{surf}$ applies. a is an adjustable parameter to fit the scale of the experiments and thus have a unit of mA times number of sites per cm^2 . b is a dimensionless adjustable parameter which governs the diffusion limitation of each individual site with $b \lesssim 1$ being very diffusion limited as neighboring sites compete for the available reactants. ΔG_{opt} is the optimum adsorption energy as relative to the adsorption on Pt(111). When not fitted, b and ΔG_{opt} was set to 0.5 and 0.1 eV, respectively. The derivation of the equations is detailed for acidic ORR

elsewhere^[39] and remains relevant for alkaline conditions^[40] as well. The fitting procedure of the predictive models is described in Supporting Information.

This theory-derived model with few adjustable parameters is highly advantageous as the transparency and physical understanding of the predictions are retained, whereas applying models with a higher number of adjustable parameters can partially obscure these insights. However, for comparison, we also benchmarked a number of widely used regression algorithms, including multiple linear regression, Gaussian process regression, gradient boosted decision trees, and random forest.

Table S2 summarizes the performance of combinations of input features and prediction models. First of all, we observed that it is generally an advantage to input both the *OH and *O adsorption energy distributions, which appear logical as more information should lead to better predictions. Secondly, the most accurate MAE of 0.042 mA/cm² is obtained using the theory-derived model described above and solely fitting parameters a and b to the gross adsorption energy distributions of *OH and *O. As expected from the SDC experiments, b is fitted to a high value close to one, as seen in Figure 3, which underlines that we are dealing with a significantly diffusion limited surface environment. This limits the per-site-activity and indicates that a broad range of surface sites take part in catalyzing the reaction. By visualizing the contribution of each site to j in equation 2, this is readily recognized as the “volcano”, symptomatic of the Sabatier expression, and assumes a broad and rounded shape by fitting a and b , as shown in Figure 3b.

Almost the same degree of accuracy is achieved by fitting the histogram of binned gross adsorption energies with multiple linear regression, as seen in Figure S14. Since the theory-derived model relies on the assumption that each adsorption energy contributes a certain amount to the total current density, the flexibility of a multiple linear model should be able to capture those contributions. This is apparent in Figure S15, where the significant contributions to the predicted current density originate from sites with adsorption energies around 0.1 eV. These results support the idea that catalysis, even on an alloy surface with a potentially staggering number of unique binding sites, can be adequately described by a descriptor variable correlated with the catalytic activity, given that we can estimate the abundance of each site.

From Table S2, we also observe that the gross adsorption energies generally result in better predictions than using the net adsorption energies as input. This could indicate that the adsorbate blocking scheme that we have previously used might be too restrictive and that the weak-binding site motifs are not as unavailable for adsorption as we presumed. Lastly, we also see that applying multiple linear regression or Gaussian process regression to the volume compositions actually performs well with an MAE of 0.052 mA/cm², which speaks to the simplicity and smoothness of the activity “landscape” in this composition space. However, using the linear regression model with volume compositions will also have limitations close to the corners of the composition space in proximity to the pure elements. The linear

Figure 3. a,c-f) Parity plots showing predicted current density against experimentally observed current density. Each plot shows a fold in the cross-validation scheme where a single materials library was held as a test set and the remaining libraries were used to fit the *a* and *b* terms in equations 1 and 2. All alloy compositions are colored according to the fraction of Ru (capped at 75%) as illustrated by the colorbar. Versions showing the Ag, Pd, and Pt content are available in Figures S11–13. The three-dimensional simplexes show the library's position in the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru composition space. b) Predicted gross adsorption energy distributions of *OH and *O on the measurement area with volume composition Ag₂₂Pd₁₄Pt₅₄Ru₁₁ plotted as histograms. The contribution to the current density, *j_i*, of a single site, *i*, is overlaid as a dashed line showing the rounded and broad “volcano” shape arising from the high value of *b*.

regression model will inherently not be accurate everywhere unless the observed catalytic activity is only “the sum of its parts,” which is incorrect as favorable ligand effects are commonly known to enhance the performance of catalyst materials.^[41–44]

The clear advantage of using the adsorption energies as input features over bulk composition is the ability to extrapolate the predictions to uncharted parts of the composition space where experiments have yet to be obtained. To investigate this capability, we excluded the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru library and flipped the training and test sets of the aforementioned cross-validation: the adjustable parameters of the theory-derived model were then fitted to a single ternary materials library, and the model was evaluated on the remaining three libraries, which contain elements not present in the training library.

As seen from Figure S16, this leads to a ≈50% increase in error with a total MAE of 0.063 mA/cm², but the model is still able to make qualitatively good predictions despite the disadvantage of the domain-shift, which is not possible without the added information of the adsorption energies. It was not possible to achieve comparable accuracy with the combination of gross adsorption energies and any of the other prediction models as they exhibited overfitting of the single materials library.

Figures S17–S20 show the capacity of the theory-derived model to extrapolate the trend of catalytic activity in the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru composition space: The best possible extrapolation from experimental data is a Gaussian process regression model fitted to the bulk compositions of all materials libraries. When we compare this to the predictions for the whole ternary simplex in the cross-validation procedure, we observe excellent qualitative agreement with the theory-derived model. Furthermore, the best-performing model of this work appears to be a significant improvement over the model used previously,^[34,35,39] although the predicted optima do not differ significantly.

Despite the low MAE demonstrated, there are clearly trends in the experimental results that elude explanation by any combination of input features and model choice. Notably, there are composition gradients where the predicted current density changes while the experimentally observed current density remains constant. This is most clearly seen in Figure 3e, where a “J-like” shape especially appears for the Ag–Pt–Ru library. Contrarily, in Figure 3d, we see the experimental current density of Ag–Pd–Pt increase without a comparable increase in the predicted current density. We attribute these discrepancies to deviations in the surface composition during reaction conditions from the as-deposited volume composition.

Figure 4. a) The two-dimensional simplexes constituting the ternary sides of the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru composition space and all sampled alloy compositions colored according to the measured current density at 850 mV vs. RHE. b) The same simplexes as above after a composition search procedure, where each measured current density was allowed to move to nearby alloy compositions within five at.% to find the best fit between measurement and prediction. Details on this procedure are provided in the Supporting Information.

In the case of Ag–Pt–Ru, the experimental results point to a constant amount of active sites on the surface, even though we expect the change in volume composition to result in an increase of favorable sites on the surface. It is worth noting that it is not necessarily the same active sites, as different active sites could be gained at the same rate as others are lost when changing alloy composition. However, here it seems probable that the surface expresses a higher fraction of Pt than the volume composition warrants. In the case of Ag–Pd–Pt, changes in the surface that we predict to be irrelevant to the activity are causing an increased current density. For this library, we observe the activity to be heavily correlated with the fraction of Pd, as seen in Figure S8b. This is likely due to the ligand effect of Ag interacting unfavorably with neighboring Pt-sites by making them bind the reaction intermediates too strongly.^[39] In contrast, Pd, which binds *OH a bit too weakly, benefits from this interaction, and therefore the observed discrepancy would most likely be due to an unexpected increase in surface Pd.

Both cases could have resulted from the leaching of certain elements during the reaction or local diffusion within the top layers to minimize surface energy, e.g., surface Ru burrowing into the bulk layers as Ru has the highest fcc(111) surface energy of the elements.^[45] Alternatively, because these discrepancies are most noticeable in alloys with high Ag and Ru content, they could be attributed to oxide formation as the surfaces were exposed to ambient air prior to catalytic measurements.^[46,47] At this juncture, it has not

been possible to assert the surface composition with sufficient depth resolution after the electrochemical measurements. However, it is possible to supplement the analysis of the changing surface composition during reaction conditions: The proposed changes can be visualized by letting the alloy compositions of the experimental samples “wander” by altering the element fractions in increments of up to five at. % until a satisfactory match between the predicted and observed current density is achieved. This method yields a qualitative overview of the general trend in the changing surface composition during reaction conditions: In Figure 4a, the as-deposited alloy compositions are shown, and Figure 4b shows the alloy compositions after letting them move to fit the predictions of the theory-derived model. For the Ag–Pd–Ru and Ag–Pt–Ru libraries, it is observed that the compositions have migrated away from the Ag–Ru edge, and surfaces with higher fractions of Pd and Pt, respectively, would better fit the predicted values. Additionally, we see that the measurement areas on the Ag–Pd–Pt library could, to some degree, have decomposed into the pure elements as the sampled compositions have moved towards the corners of the simplex. As seen in Figure 3f, the Pd–Pt–Ru library has the lowest test MAE, and thus the compositions do not see significant adjustment in Figure 4b, possibly indicating that the discrepancy between as-deposited volume composition and predicted current density values is caused by some interaction between Ag and Ru.

Conclusion

In summary, we have shown that using the inferred adsorption energy distributions of the reaction intermediates *OH and *O as the descriptors of CCSS surface properties yields better accuracy in the prediction of ORR activity than solely using the alloy composition as an input feature. Consequently, electrochemical oxygen reduction appears to largely occur on a single site, so the reaction rate can be described as the sum of the reaction rates of all available binding sites in accordance with the descriptor-based approach of catalytic theory, even if the surface is extremely heterogeneous in terms of surface atom arrangements.

We also demonstrated that the adsorption energy distributions allow predictions of ORR activity for multinary alloys with new elements that have yet to be included in experiments, making this approach a viable strategy for computational catalyst discovery for high-entropy materials before conducting high-throughput experiments. However, we argue that there will likely be a discrepancy of composition between the as-deposited volume composition and the atomic surface environment during reaction conditions, potentially reducing the heterogeneity of the surface. Further investigation into this is needed to push the accuracy of the predicted catalytic activity to higher levels.

Acknowledgements

CMC, JKP, and JR acknowledge support from the Danish National Research Foundation Center for High-Entropy Alloy Catalysis (CHEAC) DNRF-149 and from VILLUM FONDEN (research grant 9455). OK and WS acknowledge financial support by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (CasCat [833408]) and the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) under Germany's Excellence Strategy-EXC 2033-390677874-RESOLV.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data and analysis that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/634844469>.

Keywords: Catalyst Discovery · Combinatorial Co-Sputtering · Density Functional Theory · High-Entropy Alloys · Scanning Droplet Cell

- [1] Y. Yao, Z. Huang, P. Xie, S. D. Lacey, R. J. Jacob, H. Xie, F. Chen, A. Nie, T. Pu, M. Rehwoldt, D. Yu, M. R. Zachariah, C.

- Wang, R. Shahbazian-Yassar, J. Li, L. Hu, *Science* **2018**, 359, 1489–1494.
- [2] S. Gao, S. Hao, Z. Huang, Y. Yuan, S. Han, L. Lei, X. Zhang, R. Shahbazian-Yassar, J. Lu, *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, 11, 2016.
- [3] B. Wang, C. Wang, X. Yu, Y. Cao, L. Gao, C. Wu, Y. Yao, Z. Lin, Z. Zou, *Nat. Synth.* **2022**, 1, 138–146.
- [4] F. Waag, Y. Li, A. R. Zieffuß, E. Bertin, M. Kamp, V. Duppel, G. Marzun, L. Kienle, S. Barcikowski, B. Gökce, *RSC Adv.* **2019**, 9, 18547–18558.
- [5] M. Liu, Z. Zhang, F. Okejiri, S. Yang, S. Zhou, S. Dai, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, 6, 1900015.
- [6] T. Li, Y. Yao, Z. Huang, P. Xie, Z. Liu, M. Yang, J. Gao, K. Zeng, A. H. Brozena, G. Pastel, M. Jiao, Q. Dong, J. Dai, S. Li, H. Zong, M. Chi, J. Luo, Y. Mo, G. Wang, C. Wang, R. Shahbazian-Yassar, L. Hu, *Nat. Catal.* **2021**, 4, 62–70.
- [7] K. Zeng, J. Zhang, W. Gao, L. Wu, H. Liu, J. Gao, Z. Li, J. Zhou, T. Li, Z. Liang, B. Xu, Y. Yao, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2022**, 32, 2204643.
- [8] H.-J. Qiu, G. Fang, Y. Wen, P. Liu, G. Xie, X. Liu, S. Sun, J. *Mater. Chem. A* **2019**, 7, 6499–6506.
- [9] Z. Rao, P.-Y. Tung, R. Xie, Y. Wei, H. Zhang, A. Ferrari, T. P. C. Klaver, F. Körmann, P. T. Sukumar, A. Kwiatkowski Da Silva, Y. Chen, Z. Li, D. Ponge, J. Neugebauer, O. Gutfleisch, S. Bauer, D. Raabe, *Science* **2022**, 378, 78–85.
- [10] L. Sun, R. J. Cava, *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **2019**, 3, 090301.
- [11] H. Li, Y. Han, H. Zhao, W. Qi, D. Zhang, Y. Yu, W. Cai, S. Li, J. Lai, B. Huang, L. Wang, *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, 11, 5437.
- [12] Y. Yao, Z. Liu, P. Xie, Z. Huang, T. Li, D. Morris, Z. Finfrock, J. Zhou, M. Jiao, J. Gao, Y. Mao, J. Miao, P. Zhang, R. Shahbazian-Yassar, C. Wang, G. Wang, L. Hu, *Sci. Adv.* **2020**, 6, eaaz0510.
- [13] S. Nellaiappan, N. K. Katiyar, R. Kumar, A. Parui, K. D. Malviya, K. G. Pradeep, A. K. Singh, S. Sharma, C. S. Tiwary, K. Biswas, *ACS Catal.* **2020**, 10, 3658–3663.
- [14] H. Li, H. Huang, Y. Chen, F. Lai, H. Fu, L. Zhang, N. Zhang, S. Bai, T. Liu, *Adv. Mater.* **2023**, 35, 2209242.
- [15] L. Sharma, N. K. Katiyar, A. Parui, R. Das, R. Kumar, C. S. Tiwary, A. K. Singh, A. Halder, K. Biswas, *Nano Res.* **2022**, 15, 4799–4806.
- [16] R. Yao, Y. Zhou, H. Shi, W. Wan, Q. Zhang, L. Gu, Y. Zhu, Z. Wen, X. Lang, Q. Jiang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2021**, 31, 2009613.
- [17] Z. Jin, J. Lv, H. Jia, W. Liu, H. Li, Z. Chen, X. Lin, G. Xie, X. Liu, S. Sun, H. Qiu, *Small* **2019**, 15, 1904180.
- [18] K. Mori, N. Hashimoto, N. Kamiuchi, H. Yoshida, H. Kobayashi, H. Yamashita, *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, 12, 3884.
- [19] J. K. Pedersen, T. A. A. Batchelor, A. Bagger, J. Rossmeisl, *ACS Catal.* **2020**, 10, 2169–2176.
- [20] K. L. Svane, J. Rossmeisl, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2022**, 61, e202201146.
- [21] J.-W. Yeh, S.-K. Chen, S.-J. Lin, J.-Y. Gan, T.-S. Chin, T.-T. Shun, C.-H. Tsau, S.-Y. Chang, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* **2004**, 6, 299–303.
- [22] B. Cantor, I. T. H. Chang, P. Knight, A. J. B. Vincent, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* **2004**, 375–377, 213–218.
- [23] E. B. Tetteh, L. Banko, O. A. Krysiak, T. Löffler, B. Xiao, S. Varhade, S. Schumacher, A. Savan, C. Andronesco, A. Ludwig, W. Schuhmann, *Electrochem. Sci. Adv.* **2022**, 2, e2100105.
- [24] T. A. A. Batchelor, J. K. Pedersen, S. H. Winther, I. E. Castelli, K. W. Jacobsen, J. Rossmeisl, *Joule* **2019**, 3, 834–845.
- [25] T. Löffler, A. Ludwig, J. Rossmeisl, W. Schuhmann, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2021**, 60, 26894–26903.
- [26] J. N. Brønsted, *Chem. Rev.* **1928**, 5, 213–338.
- [27] M. G. Evans, M. Polanyi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.* **1938**, 34, 11–24.
- [28] P. Sabatier, *La Catalyze En Chimie Organique*, Librairie Polytechnique, Paris et Liège **1913**.

- [29] J. K. Nørskov, J. Rossmeisl, A. Logadottir, L. Lindqvist, J. R. Kitchin, T. Bligaard, H. Jónsson, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2004**, *108*, 17886–17892.
- [30] A. Kulkarni, S. Siahrostami, A. Patel, J. K. Nørskov, *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 2302–2312.
- [31] W. T. Hong, M. Risch, K. A. Stoerzinger, A. Grimaud, J. Suntivich, Y. Shao-Horn, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2015**, *8*, 1404–1427.
- [32] I. E. L. Stephens, A. S. Bondarenko, U. Grønbjerg, J. Rossmeisl, I. Chorkendorff, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2012**, *5*, 6744.
- [33] J. Greeley, I. E. L. Stephens, A. S. Bondarenko, T. P. Johansson, H. A. Hansen, T. F. Jaramillo, J. Rossmeisl, I. Chorkendorff, J. K. Nørskov, *Nat. Chem.* **2009**, *1*, 552–556.
- [34] J. K. Pedersen, C. M. Clausen, O. A. Krysiak, B. Xiao, T. A. A. Batchelor, T. Löffler, V. A. Mints, L. Banko, M. Arenz, A. Savan, W. Schuhmann, A. Ludwig, J. Rossmeisl, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2021**, *60*, 24144–24152.
- [35] T. A. A. Batchelor, T. Löffler, B. Xiao, O. A. Krysiak, V. Strottkötter, J. K. Pedersen, C. M. Clausen, A. Savan, Y. Li, W. Schuhmann, J. Rossmeisl, A. Ludwig, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2021**, *60*, 6932–6937.
- [36] L. Banko, O. A. Krysiak, J. K. Pedersen, B. Xiao, A. Savan, T. Löffler, S. Baha, J. Rossmeisl, W. Schuhmann, A. Ludwig, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2022**, *12*, 2103312.
- [37] K. Niu, B. Yang, J. Cui, J. Jin, X. Fu, Q. Zhao, J. Zhang, *J. Power Sources* **2013**, *243*, 65–71.
- [38] M. M. Hossen, K. Artyushkova, P. Atanassov, A. Serov, *J. Power Sources* **2018**, *375*, 214–221.
- [39] C. M. Clausen, M. L. S. Nielsen, J. K. Pedersen, J. Rossmeisl, *High Entropy Alloys Mater.* **2023**, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44210-022-00006-4>.
- [40] K. D. Jensen, J. Tymoczko, J. Rossmeisl, A. S. Bandarenka, I. Chorkendorff, M. Escudero-Escribano, I. E. L. Stephens, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 2800–2805.
- [41] J. A. Zamora Zeledón, M. B. Stevens, G. T. K. K. Gunasooriya, A. Gallo, A. T. Landers, M. E. Kreider, C. Hahn, J. K. Nørskov, T. F. Jaramillo, *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12*, 620.
- [42] X. Wu, F. Chen, N. Zhang, Y. Lei, Y. Jin, A. Qaseem, R. L. Johnston, *Small* **2017**, *13*, 1603387.
- [43] A. Holewinski, J.-C. Idrobo, S. Linic, *Nat. Chem.* **2014**, *6*, 828–834.
- [44] J. Huang, L. Sementa, Z. Liu, G. Barcaro, M. Feng, E. Liu, L. Jiao, M. Xu, D. Leshchev, S.-J. Lee, M. Li, C. Wan, E. Zhu, Y. Liu, B. Peng, X. Duan, W. A. Goddard, A. Fortunelli, Q. Jia, Y. Huang, *Nat. Catal.* **2022**, *5*, 513–523.
- [45] R. Tran, Z. Xu, B. Radhakrishnan, D. Winston, W. Sun, K. A. Persson, S. P. Ong, *Sci. Data* **2016**, *3*, 160080.
- [46] N. A. Shumilova, G. V. Zhutaeva, M. P. Tarasevich, *Electrochim. Acta* **1966**, *11*, 967–974.
- [47] J. S. Spendelov, A. Wieckowski, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2007**, *9*, 2654–2675.

Manuscript received: May 22, 2023

Accepted manuscript online: August 3, 2023

Version of record online: August 22, 2023